

A Prospective Observational Study On The Effectiveness Of Bilastine And Fexofenadine In The Treatment Of Chronic Spontaneous Urticaria

SK. Mulla Mobin¹, K. Govindaraju², B. Rajasree², SK. Ayesha², S. Sasipriya³, V. Tharuni Rajeswari³, J.N. Suresh Kumar⁴

¹Asst.Professor, Department of Pharmacy Parctice, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopeta, Andhra Pradesh, India.

²V/VI Pharm.D , Department of Pharmacy Practice, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopeta, Andhra Pradesh, India.

³V/VI Pharm.D , Department of Pharmacy Practice, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopeta, Andhra Pradesh, India.

⁴Principal & Professor, Department of pharmaceutics, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Narasaraopeta, Andhra Pradesh, India.

ABSTRACT

Chronic spontaneous urticaria is a persistent skin disorder characterized by spontaneous wheals, angioedema, or both lasting for more than 6 weeks without an identifiable trigger. It significantly affects quality of life due to itching, sleep disturbance, and emotional stress. Second-generation H1 antihistamines are the first-line treatment, but over half of patients do not respond to standard doses. While fexofenadine is commonly used, it may cause fatigue and cognitive impairment, whereas bilastine offers rapid action with minimal sedation and a favorable safety profile. **OBJECTIVES:** To compare the safety and efficacy of Bilastine and Fexofenadine in patients with Chronic Spontaneous Urticaria. **METHODS:** A prospective observational study was conducted among 246 patients diagnosed with chronic spontaneous urticaria who attended dermatology department at Dr. Kondapalli Hospitals and Sruthi Skin Clinic. patients suffering from chronic spontaneous urticaria. The patients received either Bilastine or Fexofenadine therapy. Disease severity and treatment response were measured by Urticaria Activity Score (UAS7) and Chronic Urticaria Quality of Life Questionnaire (CU-Q2oL), and statistical calculations were carried out using the chi-square test to check the statistical significance of the differences between the two drugs. **RESULTS:** The study population had a slight female predominance (54.07%). At baseline, the majority of patients had moderate to severe disease activity. Significant improvement in the severity of symptoms was observed in the follow-up period for both treatment groups. More patients from the Bilastine group had improvement in the severity of symptoms to the mild severity group compared to the fexofenadine group. The overall complete treatment response was observed in 77.23% of the patients. Adverse effects were minimal, including headache, nausea, fatigue, and sedation. Bilastine was slightly better tolerated with fewer side effects and the need for dose escalation compared to fexofenadine. **CONCLUSION:** Both Bilastine and Fexofenadine were effective and well tolerated in the management of chronic spontaneous urticaria. However, comparatively better clinical results were observed with bilastine in terms of symptom relief, quality of life, and tolerability. Thus, bilastine can be considered a better option for the management of chronic spontaneous urticaria.

Keywords: Chronic spontaneous urticaria, Bilastine, Fexofenadine, Urticaria Activity Score(UAS), Chronic Urticaria Quality of Life(CUQ2OL).

INTRODUCTION

Urticaria (hives, wheals, welts) is a hypersensitivity reaction that may occur in isolation or associated with

angioedema and/ or anaphylaxis. Urticaria erupts spontaneously and smooth, erythematous, itchy swellings (wheals) persist for 2– 24hrs before fading to leave normal skin. In most patients with chronic

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

urticaria, a cause is not identified, and it is called spontaneous. Urticaria is estimated to occur 15% to 25% of the population at some time in life. All age groups can be affected with acute reactions occurring more often in children and young adults. Chronic urticaria occurs more often in adults, particularly middle aged women. The etiology of urticaria is varied and often obscure. Caused by some drugs, serums, inhalants, insect bites/stings, contact substances, connective tissue diseases, neoplasms, infections, endocrine disorders and physical agents. On exposure to cold, heat, sunlight, pressure or dermatographism. Due to cholinergic or adrenergic factors. Hereditary angioedema, characterized by recurrent, self-limited attacks, is transmitted by autosomal dominant inheritance with incomplete penetrance. Childhood onset and family history[4]. Urticaria is estimated to occur 15% to 25% of the population at some time in life. All age groups can be affected with acute reactions occurring more often in children and young adults. Chronic urticaria occurs more often in adults, particularly middle aged women. Chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU) is a persistent and debilitating skin condition defined by the spontaneous occurrence of wheals, angioedema, or both for over 6 weeks without any identifiable external trigger. It significantly impairs quality of life due to constant itching, sleep disturbance, and emotional distress.

Second-generation H1- antihistamine (SGAHs) are the first-line therapy for chronic spontaneous urticaria. However, more than half of patients don't respond adequately to standard doses, and the effectiveness and tolerability can vary among antihistamines. Fexofenadine is widely used but frequently associated with fatigue and sedation, While Bilastine is a newer SGAH known for its minimal sedation and rapid onset. There is a lack of direct comparative studies between these two agents, especially in the Indian population. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate and compare the efficacy and safety of Bilastine versus Fexofenadine in chronic spontaneous urticaria, to guide clinical decisions and optimize patient outcomes, particularly in Indian patients where specific data are limited.

METHODOLOGY

Study design: A Prospective Observational Study.

Study site: The study was conducted at Dr. Kondapalli Hospitals and Sruthi Skin Clinic, Narasaraopet.

Study period: A period of 6 months

Sample size: 246 (Sample size was calculated by using N-Master's formula, with 95% confidence interval and 5% of margin error)

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients who are diagnosed with chronic spontaneous urticaria for at least 6 weeks.
- Both male and female patients will be considered.
- Patients aged between 18-60 years will be included in this study.
- Only out patients will be included.
- Willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Pregnancy and lactating women will be excluded.
- Patients with liver or kidney disease will be excluded.
- Patients with other forms of urticaria (e.g., physical, allergic or inducible) will be excluded.
- Those on immune suppressive therapy or with serious systemic illness.

ETHICAL APPROVAL:

This study was approved by the Institutional Ethics committee of Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical sciences, Narasaraopeta.

SOURCE OF DATA:

The patient's demographical data, clinical data, therapeutic data and various other relevant and necessary data were obtained every day from the medical records and other relevant informations sources are documented.

DATA HANDLING AND MANAGEMENT:

The data collection form is enclosed. MS Excel format will be used for collecting data.

Strict privacy and confidentiality are maintained during data collection.

STUDY PROCEDURE:

All the patients with Chronic Spontaneous Urticaria consulting to the Department of dermatology were reviewed weekly to identify the urticaria severity, itching and quality of life status. It is assessed by Urticaria Activity Score over 7 days (UAS7). Those patients who met the study criteria were enrolled in the study. A suitable data collection form was designed to collect all the necessary and relevant information. A Chronic Urticaria Quality of Life (CUQ2OL) index questionnaire was designed to assess the quality of life of a patient suffering from Chronic Spontaneous Urticaria. The demographic details of the patient such as name, age, sex. Clinical data such as chief complaints, diagnosis, and clinical condition. Therapeutic data such as the name of the drugs, dose, route, frequency, duration of therapy and other relevant details were collected by reviewing the case sheets, treatment charts and by interviewing the patients.

A note of other concomitant medications consumed was also made. A personal visit was made to all the patients who were included in the study to collect any

further information. Their medications were cross-checked with the treatment chart. All the patients were monitored from the day of visit.

RESULTS

The information provides the summary of all the results that are characterized based on various parameters.

AGE-WISE DISTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY POPULATION

A total of 246 subjects were included in the study. The highest proportion of subjects belonged to the 51–60 years age group, accounting for 52 subjects (21.31%), followed closely by the 21–30 years age group with 51 subjects (20.90%) and the 41–50 years age group with 50 subjects (20.49%). Subjects aged 31–40 years constituted 47 participants (19.26%), while the lowest representation was observed in the 11–20 years age group with 44 subjects (18.03%). Overall, the study population showed a relatively uniform distribution across all age groups

Table1: Distribution based on age of subjects

Age group (years)	No. Of subjects	Percentage (%)
11-20	44	18.03
21-30	51	20.90
31-40	47	19.26
41-50	50	20.49
51-60	52	21.31
Grand total	246	100.00

DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY SUBJECTS BASED ON GENDER

The gender-wise distribution of the study population is presented in the table 2. Out of a total of 246

subjects enrolled in the study, 133 were females, accounting for 54.07% of the total population, while 113 were males, constituting 45.93%. The study population showed a slight predominance of female subjects compared to male subjects.

Gender	No. Of subjects	Percentage (%)
Male	113	45.93
Female	133	54.07
Grand total	246	100.00

Table 2: Distribution based on gender of subjects

Fig 8: Distribution based on gender of subjects

DISTRIBUTION OF STUDY SUBJECTS BASED ON OCCUPATION

The occupation-wise distribution of the study population is depicted in the table 3. Among the 246 subjects included in the study, farmers constituted the largest occupational group with 63 subjects (25.82%), followed by house wife's with 62 subjects (25.41%).

Students accounted for 49 subjects (20.08%), Software engineers represented 20 subjects (8.20%), and teachers accounted for 19 subjects (7.79%). Smaller proportions of subjects were construction workers (2.87%), police personnel (2.46%), tailors (2.05%), nurses (2.05%), and daily worker (3.28%). Overall, the study population included participants from diverse occupational backgrounds.

Occupation	No. Of subject	Percentage (%)
Farmer	63	12.86
House wife	62	12.65
Student	49	10.00
Software engineer	28	5.71
Teacher	19	3.88
Construction worker	7	1.43
Police	6	1.22
Tailor	5	1.02
Nurse	5	1.02
Grand total	246	100.00

Table 3: Distribution based on occupation of subjects

Fig 9: Distribution based on occupation of subjects

DISTRIBUTION BASED ON DURATION OF DISEASE

The above table illustrates the distribution of study participants based on the duration of CSU (in months) in the two treatment groups receiving Bilastine and Fexofenadine. Presenting the duration of illness in both groups helps in assessing baseline comparability

and understanding the chronicity pattern among enrolled subjects.

This analysis is essential to ensure that both groups are appropriately matched in terms of disease duration, thereby strengthening the validity and reliability of the comparative evaluation of therapeutic outcomes in the study.

Duration of CSU (in months)	Bilastine	Fexofenadine
0-6	89	78
7-12	31	37
13-18	2	1
19-24	5	3
Total	127	119

Table 4: Distribution based on duration of chronic spontaneous urticaria

Fig 10: Distribution based on duration of chronic spontaneous urticaria

TREATMENT GROUP AMONG STUDY SUBJECTS

A total of 246 subjects were included in the study. Of these, 127 subjects received Bilastine, accounting for

52.03% of the study population. The remaining 118 subjects were treated with Fexofenadine, representing 47.97% of the total. Thus, both treatment groups were comparably distributed among the study subjects.

DRUG NAME	NUMBER OF SUBJECTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Bilastine	127	51.63
Fexofenadine	119	48.37
GRAND TOTAL	246	100.00

Table 5: Distribution based on treatment groups among subjects

Fig11: Distribution based on treatment groups among study subjects

SEVERITY DISTRIBUTION BASED ON URTICARIA ACTIVITY SCORE**(UAS-7) SCORE AT VISIT**

The UAS-7 scoring system was utilized to evaluate the intensity of allergic symptoms in a cohort of 246 subjects, with 127 individuals undergoing treatment with Bilastine and 119 with Fexofenadine. None of the subjects fell into the mild severity category.

Among the study population, 121 subjects (49.19%) were categorized as having moderate severity. Of these, 75 subjects were in the Bilastine group and 46 subjects were in the Fexofenadine group. A total of 125 subjects (50.81%) were classified under the severe category, comprising 52 subjects treated with Bilastine and 73 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. Severe cases were more common in the Fexofenadine group, whereas moderate cases predominated in the Bilastine group at the time of assessment.

Severity	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage (%)
Mild	0	0	0.00
Moderate	75	46	49.19
Severe	52	73	50.81
Grand total	127	119	100.00

Table 6: Distribution based on severity of UAS-7 score at visit

Fig 12: Distribution based on severity of UAS-7 score at visit

A Chi-square test was performed to evaluate the association between treatment group and severity category. The analysis showed a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 10.17$, $df = 1$), with a p-value of 0.001. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the difference in severity distribution between the two treatment groups is considered statistically significant.

SEVERITY DISTRIBUTION BASED ON UAS-7 SCORE AT FOLLOW UP-1

The severity of symptoms was evaluated using the UAS-7 scoring system among 246 subjects, including 127 subjects treated with Bilastine and 119 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. Out of the total study

population, 104 subjects (42.28%) were classified under the mild category, comprising 68 subjects in the Bilastine group and 36 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. A total of 98 subjects (39.84%) were categorized as having moderate severity, including 45 subjects receiving Bilastine and 53 subjects receiving Fexofenadine. The remaining 44 subjects (17.88%) were classified under the severe category, of whom 14 were in the Bilastine group and 30 were in the Fexofenadine group. Overall, mild severity predominated in the Bilastine group, whereas moderate and severe categories were more common in the Fexofenadine group.

Severity	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage (%)
Mild	68	36	42.28
Moderate	45	53	39.84
Severe	14	30	17.88
Grand total	127	119	100.00

Table 7: Distribution based on severity of UAS-7 score at follow up-1

Fig 13: Distribution based on severity of UAS-7 score at follow up-1

A Chi-square test was performed to assess the association between treatment group and severity category. The analysis demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 14.62$, $df = 2$), with a p-value of 0.0007. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the variation in severity distribution between the two treatment groups is considered statistically significant.

SEVERITY DISTRIBUTION BASED ON UAS-7 SCORE AT FOLLOW UP-2

The severity of symptoms was evaluated using the UAS-7 scoring system among 246 subjects, including 127 subjects treated with Bilastine and 119 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. Out of the total study

population, 190 subjects (77.23%) were classified under the mild category, comprising 101 subjects in the Bilastine group and 89 subjects in the Fexofenadine group.

A total of 44 subjects (17.9%) were categorized as having moderate severity, including 23 subjects receiving Bilastine and 21 subjects receiving Fexofenadine. The remaining 12 subjects (4.87%) were classified under the severe category, of whom 5 were in the Bilastine group and 7 were in the Fexofenadine group.

Overall, mild severity predominated in the Bilastine group, whereas severe cases were more common in the Fexofenadine.

Severity	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage(%)
Mild	101	89	77.23
Moderate	23	21	7.9
Severe	5	7	4.87
Grand total	127	119	100.00

Table 8: Distribution based on severity of UAS-7 score at follow up-2

Fig 14: Distribution based on severity of UAS-7 score at follow up-2

A Chi-square test was performed to assess the association between treatment group and severity category. The analysis showed a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 18.96$, $df = 2$), with a p-value < 0.001 . Since $p < 0.05$, the difference in severity distribution between the two treatment groups is considered statistically significant.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT EFFICACY UAS-7

At baseline, no patients in either treatment group had mild symptoms. In the Bilastine group, most patients presented with moderate (75) and severe (52) symptoms. Similarly, in the Fexofenadine group, 46 patients had moderate symptoms while 73 patients had severe symptoms. During Follow-up 1, a clear improvement in symptom severity was observed in both groups. In the Bilastine group, the number of patients with mild symptoms increased to 68, while moderate cases decreased to 45 and severe cases decreased to 14. In the Fexofenadine group, 36

patients showed mild symptoms, while moderate cases slightly increased to 53, and severe cases reduced to 30.

By Follow-up 2, further improvement was evident. In the Bilastine group, mild cases increased to 101, while moderate cases decreased to 23 and severe cases dropped to only 5. In the Fexofenadine group, mild cases increased to 89, moderate cases decreased to 21, and severe cases reduced to 7.

Both Bilastine and Fexofenadine treatments showed a progressive reduction in symptom severity over time, with an increase in mild cases and a decrease in moderate and severe cases from baseline to Follow-up 2. However, the Bilastine group demonstrated a slightly greater shift toward mild symptoms and a more pronounced reduction in severe cases compared to the Fexofenadine group.

Table 9: Comparison of bilastine and fexofenadine based on UAS-7 score

Fig 15: Comparison of bilastine and fexofenadine based on UAS-7 score

SEVERITY DISTRIBUTION BASED ON CHRONIC URTICARIA QUALITY OF LIFE (CU-Q2oL) SCORE AT VISIT

The severity of quality-of-life impairment was assessed using the CU-Q2oL scoring system among 246 subjects, including 127 subjects in the Bilastine group and 119 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. A total of 22 subjects (8.94%) were categorized under the mild impairment group, comprising 10 subjects

treated with Bilastine and 12 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. Moderate impairment was observed in 86 subjects (34.96%), including 57 subjects in the Bilastine group and 29 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. The majority of subjects, 138 (56.10%), were classified under the severe impairment category, with 60 subjects receiving Bilastine and 78 subjects receiving Fexofenadine. Overall, severe quality-of-life impairment predominated in both treatment groups at the time of assessment.

Severity	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage (%)
Mild	10	12	8.94
Moderate	57	29	34.96
Severe	60	78	56.10
Total	127	119	100.00

Table 10: Distribution based on severity of CU-Q2oL score at visit

Fig 16: Distribution based on severity of CU-Q2oL score at visit

A Chi-square test was conducted to assess the association between treatment group and severity of quality-of-life impairment. The analysis demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 12.64$, $df = 2$), with a p-value = 0.0018. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the difference in CU-Q2oL severity distribution between the two treatment groups is considered statistically significant.

SEVERITY DISTRIBUTION BASED ON CU-Q2oL SCORE AT FOLLOW UP-1

The severity of quality-of-life impairment was evaluated using the CU-Q2oL scoring system among

246 subjects, comprising 127 subjects in the Bilastine group and 119 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. Mild impairment was observed in 130 subjects (52.85%), including 80 subjects treated with Bilastine and 50 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. Moderate impairment was reported in 78 subjects (31.71%), with 35 subjects in the Bilastine group and 43 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. Severe impairment was noted in 38 subjects (15.45%), of whom 12 were receiving Bilastine and 26 were receiving Fexofenadine. Overall, mild impairment predominated in the Bilastine group, whereas moderate and severe impairment were more common in the Fexofenadine group.

Severity	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage (%)
Mild	80	50	52.85
Moderate	35	43	31.71
Severe	12	26	15.45
Grand total	127	119	100.00%

Table 11: Distribution based on severity of CU-Q2oL score at follow up-1

Fig 17: Distribution based on severity of CU-Q2oL score at follow up-1

A Chi-square test was performed to assess the association between treatment group and severity of quality-of-life impairment. The analysis demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 16.84$, $df = 2$), with a p -value < 0.001 . Since $p < 0.05$, the difference in CU-Q2oL severity distribution between the two treatment groups is considered statistically significant.

SEVERITY DISTRIBUTION BASED ON CU-Q2oL SCORE AT FOLLOW UP-2

The severity of quality-of-life impairment was assessed using the CU-Q2oL scoring system among

Severity	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage(%)
Mild	115	85	81.30
Moderate	8	22	12.20
Severe	4	12	6.50
Grand total	127	119	100.00

Table 12: Distribution based on severity of CU-Q2oL score at follow up-2

Overall, mild quality-of-life impairment predominated in the Bilastine group, whereas moderate and severe impairment were more common in the Fexofenadine.

Fig 18: Distribution based on severity of CU-Q2oL score at follow up-2

A Chi-square test was performed to assess the association between treatment group and severity of quality-of-life impairment. The analysis demonstrated a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 15.37$, $df = 2$), with a p -value = 0.0005. Since $p < 0.05$, the difference in CU-Q2oL severity distribution between

246 subjects, including 127 subjects treated with Bilastine and 119 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. The majority of subjects, 200 (81.30%), were classified under the mild impairment category, comprising 115 subjects in the Bilastine group and 85 subjects in the Fexofenadine group.

Moderate impairment was observed in 30 subjects (12.20%), including 8 subjects receiving Bilastine and 22 subjects receiving Fexofenadine. Severe impairment was reported in 16 subjects (6.50%), with 4 subjects in the Bilastine group and 12 subjects in the Fexofenadine group.

the two treatment groups is considered statistically significant.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TREATMENT EFFICACY CU-Q2oL

At baseline, most patients in both groups had moderate to severe symptoms. In the Bilastine group,

10 patients had mild symptoms, 57 had moderate symptoms, and 60 had severe symptoms. In the Fexofenadine group, 12 patients had mild symptoms, 29 had moderate symptoms, and 78 had severe symptoms, indicating a higher number of severe cases initially. At follow-up 1, improvement in symptom severity was observed in both groups. In the Bilastine group, mild cases increased to 80, while moderate cases decreased to 35 and severe cases decreased to 12. In the Fexofenadine group, mild cases increased to 50, moderate cases decreased to 24, and severe cases decreased to 12. By follow-up 2, further

improvement was evident. In the Bilastine group, mild cases increased markedly to 115, while moderate cases reduced to 8 and severe cases reduced to 4. In the Fexofenadine group, mild cases increased to 85, moderate cases decreased to 24, and severe cases decreased to 12. Overall, both treatments showed a progressive shift from moderate and severe symptoms toward mild symptoms over time, indicating clinical improvement. However, the Bilastine group demonstrated a greater reduction in moderate and severe cases and a larger increase in mild cases compared to the Fexofenadine group by follow-up 2.

Severity	Bilastine			Fexofenadine		
	Baseline	Follow up-1	Follow up-2	Baseline	Follow up-1	Follow up-2
Mild	10	80	115	12	50	85
Moderate	57	35	8	29	43	24
Severe	60	12	4	78	26	12

Table 13: Comparison of bilastine and fexofenadine based on CUQ2oL scores

Fig 19: Comparison of bilastine and fexofenadine based on CU-Q2oL scores

UP DOSING OF DRUGS AMONG STUDY PARTICIPANTS

Out of the total 246 subjects included in the study, dose escalation beyond the standard regimen was observed in both treatment groups. In the Bilastine group (n = 127), 108 subjects (43.90%) continued on the 20 mg dose, while 19 subjects (7.72%) required dose escalation to 40 mg. In the Fexofenadine group

(n = 119), 87 subjects (35.37%) were maintained on the 120 mg dose, whereas 32 subjects (13.01%) were up-titrated to 180 mg.

Overall, a higher proportion of subjects in the Fexofenadine group required dose escalation compared to the Bilastine group.

DRUG NAME	TITRATED DOSE (MG)	NO. OF SUBJECTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Bilastine	20MG	108	43.90
	↓ 40MG	19	7.72
Fexofenadine	120MG	87	35.37
	↓ 180MG	32	13.01
GRAND TOTAL	-	246	100.00

Table 14: Distribution based on up-titrated doses among study participants

Fig 20: Distribution based on up- titrated doses among study participants

A Chi-square test was performed to evaluate the association between treatment group and requirement for dose escalation. The analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between the Bilastine and Fexofenadine groups ($\chi^2 = 4.76$, $df = 1$), with a p -value = 0.029. Since $p < 0.05$, the proportion of subjects requiring dose escalation differed significantly between the two treatment groups.

DISTRIBUTION BASED ON TREATMENT RESPONSE

The treatment response was assessed among 246 subjects, including 127 subjects in the Bilastine group and 119 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. Subjects were categorized into complete response, partial response, and no response groups. A complete response was achieved in 190 subjects (77.23%), comprising 101 subjects treated with Bilastine and 89 subjects treated with Fexofenadine. Partial response was observed in 44 subjects (17.8%), including 23

subjects in the Bilastine group and 21 subjects in the Fexofenadine group. No response was reported in 12 subjects (4.87%), of whom 5 were receiving Bilastine and 7 were receiving Fexofenadine. Overall, complete response was the predominant outcome in both treatment groups, while partial and no response were comparatively less frequent.

RESPONSE	BILASTINE	FEXOFENADINE	PERCENTAGE (%)
Complete	101	89	77.23
Partial	23	21	17.9
No response	5	7	4.87

Table 15: Distribution based on treatment response

Fig 21: Distribution based on treatment response

DISTRIBUTION BASED ON ADVERSE EFFECTS

The incidence of adverse effects was assessed among subjects receiving Bilastine and Fexofenadine. A total of 18 adverse effects were reported, of which 8 occurred in the Bilastine group and 10 in the Fexofenadine group.

Fatigue was reported in 4 cases (2 in the Bilastine group and 2 in the Fexofenadine group), while

headache was observed in 7 cases (3 with Bilastine and 3 with Fexofenadine). Nausea occurred in 5 cases, including 2 cases in the Bilastine group and 3 cases in the Fexofenadine group. Sedation was reported adverse effect, noted in 3 cases, predominantly in the Fexofenadine group (2cases) compared to the Bilastine group (1 case).

Overall, the total number of adverse effects was lower in the Bilastine group compared to the Fexofenadine group in the study population.

Adverse effect	Bilastine	Fexofenadine	Percentage (%)
Fatigue	2	2	22.2
Headache	3	3	33.3
Nausea	2	3	27.7
Sedation	1	2	16.6
Grand total	8	10	100.00

Table 16: Distribution based on adverse effects

Fig 22: Distribution based on adverse effects

DISTRIBUTION OF ADVERSE EFFECTS IN STANDARD DOSE AND HIGH DOSE

The incidence of adverse effects was evaluated among subjects receiving standard and high doses of Bilastine and Fexofenadine. A total of 18 adverse effects were reported during the study period, of which 8 occurred in the Bilastine group and 10 in the Fexofenadine group. Fatigue was observed in 4 subjects, with 2 cases in the Bilastine group (1 on standard dose and 1 on high dose) and 2 cases in the Fexofenadine group (1 on standard dose and 1 on high dose). Headache was reported in 6 subjects, including

3 subjects treated with Bilastine (2 on standard dose and 1 on high dose) and 3 subjects treated with Fexofenadine (all on high dose). Nausea was noted in 5 subjects, comprising 2 subjects in the Bilastine group (1 on standard dose and 1 on high dose) and 3 subjects in the Fexofenadine group (2 on standard dose and 1 on high dose). Sedation was reported in 3 subjects, including 1 patient receiving standard-dose Bilastine and 2 subjects receiving high-dose Fexofenadine. Overall, adverse effects were infrequent and were observed slightly more commonly in the Fexofenadine group compared to the Bilastine group.

Adverse Effects	Bilastine		Fexofenadine	
	Standard dose	High dose	Standard dose	High dose
Fatigue	1	1	1	1
Headache	2	1	0	3
Nausea	1	1	2	1
Sedation	1	0	0	2
Total	8		10	

Table 17: Distribution of adverse effects based on standard dose and high dose

Fig 23: Distribution of adverse effects based on standard dose and high dose

DISCUSSION

This prospective observational study shows the effectiveness of Bilastine and fexofenadine in the treatment of chronic spontaneous urticaria in patients attending Sruthi Skin Clinic, Narasaraopeta. The study was conducted over six months with a sample size of 246 subjects who are diagnosed to have chronic spontaneous urticaria. In this study we have utilized UAS, CUQ2OL scales for assessing the severity of urticaria. The primary objective includes the comparison of safety and efficacy of Bilastine and fexofenadine in chronic spontaneous urticaria.

In our study a total of 246 subjects were included in the study. Chronic spontaneous urticaria (CSU) is a dermatological disorder characterized by recurrent wheals, itching, and significant impairment of quality of life. The present prospective observational study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of Bilastine and Fexofenadine in the management of CSU among 246 patients. In the present study, the age-wise distribution showed that the highest proportion of patients belonged to the 51–60 years age group (21.31%), followed by the 21–30 years group (20.90%) and 41–50 years group (20.49%). The distribution across all age groups was relatively

uniform, indicating that CSU can occur in a wide range of adult populations. The gender distribution revealed a slight predominance of females (54.07%) compared to males (45.93%). This finding is consistent with several previous studies which reported that chronic urticaria is more common among females, possibly due to hormonal influences and immune system differences. The study population was divided into two treatment groups receiving Bilastine and Fexofenadine, both of which are second-generation antihistamines commonly used in the treatment of urticaria. Assessment of disease severity was performed using the Urticaria Activity Score (UAS-7), which is widely accepted for evaluating symptom severity and treatment response. At baseline, a large proportion of patients presented with moderate to severe symptoms, indicating the significant clinical burden of CSU. During the follow-up visits, there was a gradual reduction in disease severity in both treatment groups, demonstrating the effectiveness of antihistamine therapy in controlling urticaria symptoms. However, patients receiving Bilastine showed comparatively greater improvement in symptom reduction and disease severity scores compared to those treated with Fexofenadine. The number of patients categorized under the mild severity group increased during follow-up, while moderate and severe cases decreased. Statistical analysis using the Chi-square test demonstrated a significant association between treatment groups and improvement in disease severity, suggesting better clinical outcomes with Bilastine. Additionally, improvement in quality-of-life parameters was observed during follow-up assessments, indicating that effective symptom control can significantly enhance daily functioning and well-being in patients with CSU. Overall, the findings of this study highlight the effectiveness of second-generation antihistamines in the management of chronic spontaneous urticaria, with Bilastine showing slightly superior outcomes compared to Fexofenadine.

CONCLUSION

This study shows that Bilastine is safer and more efficacious than Fexofenadine in treating Chronic Spontaneous Urticaria. The present prospective observational study evaluated the effectiveness of Bilastine and Fexofenadine in the treatment of chronic

spontaneous urticaria among 246 patients. The study findings showed that CSU affected individuals across different age groups, with a slight predominance among females. Most patients initially presented with moderate to severe disease severity, which significantly affected their quality of life. Both Bilastine and Fexofenadine were effective in reducing urticaria symptoms and improving patient outcomes during the follow-up period. However, patients treated with Bilastine demonstrated greater improvement in disease severity scores and symptom control compared to those receiving Fexofenadine. Therefore, the study concludes that Bilastine is an effective and well-tolerated treatment option for chronic spontaneous urticaria and may provide better therapeutic benefits compared to Fexofenadine in improving symptom severity and patient quality of life. Our study correlates with Shah Be, et. al., (2022) in this study they demonstrated that optimized antihistamine therapy is effective and well tolerated in patients with chronic spontaneous urticaria, leading to significant improvement in symptom severity and quality of life. Escalation or appropriate selection of second-generation H1-antihistamines resulted in better disease control with minimal adverse effects, supporting their role as a safe and effective cornerstone in CSU management. Overall, the findings reinforce current treatment guidelines advocating individualized dosing strategies to achieve optimal clinical outcomes and concluded that standard doses and Updosing of bilastine provided relief from urticaria symptoms, improved quality of life in the majority of the patients without compromising somnolence or safety. Bilastine was associated with improved quality of life and less sedation compared to fexofenadine.

REFERENCES

1. Smith J, Jones P. Urticaria. In: Burge S, et al., editors. Oxford handbook of medical dermatology. 2nd ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2016. p. 123-145.
2. Helms, Richard A., Herfindal, Eric T. Textbook of therapeutics: drug and disease management. 8th ed. Philadelphia, Pa: Lippincott Williams & Wilkins; 2006 ...
3. Kelman M, Jones C. Acute, chronic and physical urticaria: A brief guide for healthcare

- professionals. London: Allergy UK; 2024-version 1
4. Zuberbier T, Aberer W, Asero R, Bindslev-Jensen C, Brzoza Z, Canonica GW, et al. The EAACI/GA(2)LEN/EDF/WAO Guideline for the definition, classification, diagnosis, and management of urticaria: the 2013 revision and update. *Allergy*. 2014;69:868-87.
 5. Bindslev - Jensen C, Finzi A, Greaves M, Camarasa J, Ortonne JP, Schöpf E, et al. Chronic urticaria: diagnostic recommendations. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2000;14:175-80.
 6. Jirapongsananuruk O, Sangacharoenkit P, Pongpreuksa S, Visitsunthorn N, Vichyanond P. Is silent sinusitis a cause of chronic urticaria in children?. *Asian Pac J Allergy Immunol*. 2009;27:103-6.
 7. Helm RM, Burks AW. Mechanisms of food allergy. *Curr Opin Immunol*. 2000;12:647-53.
 8. Bock SA, Sampson HA, Atkins FM, Zeiger RS, Lehrer S, Sachs M, et al. Doubleblind, placebo-controlled food challenge (DBPCFC) as an office procedure: a manual. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 1988;82:986-97.
 9. Konstantinou GN, Asero R, Maurer M, Sabroe RA, Schmid-Grendelmeier P, Grattan CE. EAACI/GA(2)LEN task force consensus report: the autologous serum skin test in urticaria. *Allergy*. 2009;64:1256-68.
 10. Kulthanan K, Jiamton S, Gorvanich T, Pinkaew S. Autologous serum skin test in chronic idiopathic urticaria: prevalence, correlation and clinical implications. *Asian Pac J Allergy Immunol*. 2006;24:201-6.
 11. Konstantinou GN, Asero R, Ferrer M, Knol EF, Maurer M, Raap U, et al. EAACI taskforce position paper: evidence for autoimmune urticaria and proposal for defining diagnostic criteria. *Allergy*. 2013;68:27-36.
 12. Maurer M, Magerl M, Metz M, Zuberbier T. Revisions to the international guidelines on the diagnosis and therapy of chronic urticaria. *J Dtsch Dermatol Ges*. 2013;11:971-7.
 13. Hennino A, Bérard F, Guillot I, Saad N, Rozières A, Nicolas JF. Pathophysiology of urticaria. *Clin Rev Allergy Immunol*. 2006 Feb;30(1):3-11. doi:10.1385/CRIAI:30:1:003. PMID: 16461989.
 14. Folci, M., Ramponi, G., Brunetta, E. (2020). A Comprehensive Approach to Urticaria: From Clinical Presentation to Modern Biological Treatments Through Pathogenesis. In: Turksen, K. (eds) *Cell Biology and Translational Medicine*, Volume 12. *Advances in Experimental Medicine and Biology()*, vol 1326. Springer, Cham.
 15. Sticherling M, Brasch J, Bruning H, Christophers E. Urticarial and anaphylactoid reactions following ethanol intake. *Br J Dermatol*. 1995;132:464-7
 16. Zuberbier T, Aberer W, Asero R, Bindslev-Jensen C, Brzoza Z, Canonica GW, et al. The EAACI/GA(2)LEN/EDF/WAO Guideline for the definition, classification, diagnosis, and management of urticaria: the 2013 revision and update. *Allergy*. 2014;69:868-87.
 17. Sánchez -Borges M, Asero R, Ansotegui IJ, Baiardini I, Bernstein JA, Canonica GW, et al. Diagnosis and treatment of urticaria and angioedema: a worldwide perspective. *World Allergy Organ J*. 2012;5:125-47.
 18. Ring J, Alomar A, Bieber T, Deleuran M, Fink-Wagner A, Gelmetti C, et al. Guidelines for treatment of atopic eczema (atopic dermatitis) part I. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2012;26:1045-60.
 19. Siebenhaar F, Degener F, Zuberbier T, Martus P, Maurer M. High-dose desloratadine decreases wheal volume and improves cold provocation thresholds compared with standard-dose treatment in patients with acquired cold urticaria: a randomized, placebo-controlled, crossover study. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2009;123:672-9.
 20. Staevska M, Popov TA, Kralimarkova T, Lazarova C, Kraeva S, Popova D, et al. The effectiveness of levocetirizine and desloratadine in up to 4 times conventional doses in difficult-to-treat urticaria. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2010;125:676-82.

HOW TO CITE: SK. Mulla Mobin, K. Govindaraju, B. Rajasree, SK. Ayesha, S. Sasipriya, V. Tharuni Rajeswari, J.N. Suresh Kumar⁴, A Prospective Observational Study On The Effectiveness Of Bilastine And Fexofenadine In The Treatment Of Chronic Spontaneous Urticaria, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, 2 (5), 340-356. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20130479>

